

IMPROVEMENT OF PUBLIC RELATIONS AND ADVERTISING ACTIVITIES IN THE
FIELD OF CULTURE

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Annotation: *this article presents concepts for the development of marketing research of the cultural sphere. The specifics of marketing concepts in organizations of the art and cultural sphere are highlighted. The main focus is on the processes of forming a marketing portfolio based on the requirements and desires of customers.*

Keywords: *marketing, socio-cultural sphere, Concept, Art, Culture, Capital, segmentation, sector, market economy, cultural and spiritual goods, business, intangible.*

Democratization of society, cooperation with government agencies, public feedback, recommendations, and proceedings have become important milestones in the politics of our state today. In all areas, the adoption of decisions on the basis of direct dialogue, in consultation with the people, is an expression of the fact that the noble idea that “government agencies, and not government agencies, should be served to our people,” has become the main criterion of managerial activity.

A completely new system has been created in relation to communication with the people, solving problems that are an obstacle to improving the lifestyle, well-being of the people on the spot, acting on the basis of transparency. The people's receptions and Virtual reception of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is the basis of this system, are practically justifying itself as a kind of democratic institution for working with citizens ' appeals. In modern times, "Public Relations" technologies are also widely used in management activities, especially in the field of culture and art. In all progressive states, the legislative, executive and judicial authorities are known to practice "public relations" technologies in their activities. In this regard, the close connection of state power with the people is important in the issuance of important laws, ordinances. This technology has a great effect on management activities in order to create a good idea of each organization in the public sphere, to create public feedback, to form public opinion. The public's opinion will be published on the basis of this technology with the help of local, central media. "Public relations" technologies are a specific type of Information Technology and involve processes that enable free discussion among the factual public.

This technology can be used in conducting relations with state, non-governmental and public organizations, political parties, strengthening media relations, managing information communication and its reception by the audience, working with personnel in information centers, public inspections, ensuring close ties with sponsors, conducting visual, introducing events, managing crisis situations and other times. Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan follows the path of building a legal democratic society with bold steps, the legal foundations of every social relationship that exists in society are created, and their main directions are aimed at the social development of the individual.

In the life of society, a huge number of subjects interact with the development of a person, among which the importance of advertising products is great, which is a process in which the

human psyche is inextricably linked with the processes of formation. Because the product of advertising, in turn, affects the activity of the human mind and subconscious through various means, in turn, is manifested in the social activity of the individual in such directions as the formation of a sample (ideal), the assimilation of information, knowledge of a particular area, the expansion of the individual's worldview, the identification of need.

In conditions where the market economy is increasingly entering our lives, the demand for services, especially in the field of advertising, is increasing day by day. The advertising industry is a very complex and delicate field. Everyone who wants to work in this area should be very passionate about this area and have the ability to creativity, strive for innovation and approach their work from the very heart. It is necessary for these specialists to be able to make optimal use of existing situations, to be well versed in the specifics of advertising activities of enterprises and organizations engaged in entrepreneurial activity, to be able to draw different conclusions economically, to get creative approach.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED:

1. Urinov, Sh K. "THE MAIN CRITERIA OF CULTURAL CENTERS IN THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE ABILITY." *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology* 3.5 (2023): 52-59.
2. KO'rinov, Sh, and G. Bozorboyeva. "MADANIYAT SOHASIDA PABLIK RILEYSHNZ (JAMOATCHILIK BILAN ALOQALAR) VA REKLAMA." *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* 1.4 (2023): 217-224.
3. O'rinov, SH K., and E. Sultonmurodova. "MENEJERNING MADANIYAT SOHASIDAGI KASBIY MALAKASI, USLUBLARI VA REJALASHTIRISH." *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* 1.4 (2023): 225-230.
4. KO'rinov, Sh. "LOYIHA MENEJMENTINING ASOSIY TAMOYILLARI." *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN* 1.4 (2023): 136-143.
5. Ne'matullayeva, Sh. "MADANIYAT MARKAZLARINING PROFESSIONAL JAMOALAR BILAN HAMKORLIKNI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI." *Педагогика и психология в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования* 2.3 (2023): 25-29.
6. KO'rinov, Sh, and S. Sadullayeva. "MUZEYSHUNOSLIK ISTIQBOLLARI." *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI* 3.26 (2023): 97-101.
7. Orinov, Sh K., and S. Rozimurodova. "Maqom San'atiga E'tibor Milliy San'atimizga E'tibor." "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. 2023.
8. O'rinov, Sh K., and G. Halimova. "HAVASKORLIK BADIY JAMOALARI TUSHUNCHASI VA FUNKSIONAL VAZIFASI." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 2. 2023.
9. KORinov, Sh, and M. Ismoilova. "BOSHQARUV KONSEPSIYASI VA ASOSIY TUSHUNCHALAR." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 62-64.
10. KORinov, Sh, and M. Hasanova. "BOSHQARUV MADANIYATI TARKIBI FUNKSIYALARI MEZONLARI-MADANIYAT MARKAZLARI MISOLIDA." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 65-66.
11. KORinov, Sh, and M. Habibullayeva. "ART MENEJER-MARKETING FAOLIYATINING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI SIFATIDA." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.2 (2023): 59-61.

12. KOrinov, Sh, and N. Jahongirova. "O'ZBEKISTONDA TEATR FAOLIYATIDA MARKETINGNING RIVOJLANISHI." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.1 (2023): 161-162.
13. KOrinov, Sh, and M. Raupova. "BOZOR IQTISODIYOTI SHAROITIDA MUZEYLARNING RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.1 (2023): 116-118.
14. KOrinov, Sh. "NOANANAVIY MAYDON TOMOSHA DRAMATURGIYASIDA INVERSIYA USLUBI, KOMPOZITSION BIRLIK ASOSI." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 26.1 (2023): 113-115.
15. O'rinov, Sh K., and G. A. Nurilloeva. "TASVIRIY SAN'AT MARKETINGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALALARI." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 1. 2023.
16. O'rinov, Sh K., and X. Abduraxmonova. "MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT SOHASIDAGI BOSHQARUVNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI." *PEDAGOG* 6.1 (2023): 226-231.
17. Orinov, Sh K., and S. Boboqulova. "MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT BOSHQARUVINING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI." *ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali* (2022): 78-82.
18. Orinov, Sh K., and N. Sadriddinova. "MADANIYAT MARKAZLARIGA AHOLINI JALB ETISH OMILLARI." *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 123-129.
19. Orinov, Sh K., and E. Sultonmurodova. "XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODINING TARIXIY TARAQQIYOTI." *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 166-172.
20. Orinov, Sh K., and M. Rahmatova. "MADANIYAT VA SAN'AT MUASSASALARINI BOSHQARISHDA IJRO INTIZOMINI TATBIQ ETISH MASALALARI." *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI* (2022): 130-135.
21. Ражабов, Т. И. (2020). Тическая классификация узбекской детской народной музыки и игр. *Наука, образование и культура*, (3 (47)), 61-63.
22. Ражабов, Т. И., & Ибодов, У. Р. (2020). Обеспечение национального наследия в обучении песням бухарского детского фольклора на уроках музыки. *Вестник науки и образования*, (21-2 (99)), 55-58.
23. Ражабов, Т. И. (2021). Усовершенствование научно-методических возможностей обучения бухарским детским фольклорным песням в средней общеобразовательной школе. *Наука, техника и образование*, (2-2 (77)), 84-86.
24. Ражабов, Т. И. (2020). Педагогические возможности использования детских фольклорных песен в духовно-нравственном воспитании младших школьников. *Вестник науки и образования*, (5-2 (83)), 34-37.
25. Раджабов, Т. И. (2019). Описание вековых ценностей в песне" тутовое дерево-балх" и его место в воспитании учащейся молодежи. In *Россия-Узбекистан. Международные образовательные и социально-культурные технологии: векторы развития* (pp. 70-71).
26. Ражабов, Д. З., & Ражабов, Т. И. (2018). Формирование и развитие узбекской народной лирики. In *Международная образовательная деятельность как фактор развития и сотрудничества высших учебных заведений в современном поликультурном мире* (pp. 207-212).
27. Ражабов, Т. И. (2023). Совершенствование Механизма Духовно-Нравственного Формирования Учащихся Через Узбекские Народные Песни. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 33, 167-176.
28. Ражабов, Т. И. (2021). Ўқувчи-ёшларга ўзбек миллий мусиқа фольклори намуналари воситасида эстетик тарбия бериш. *Science and Education*, 2(11), 1094-1103.

29. Тўхтасин, Р. И. (2022). ЎЗБЕК ХАЛҚ ҚЎШИҚЛАРИ ВА ИЖРОЛАРИ ҲАҚИДА. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), (Special issue), 64-71.
30. Rajabov, T. I. The Mechanism of Teaching Uzbek Musical Folklore. Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences ISSN, 2795(546X),
31. Ражабов, Т. (2023). О ‘zbek bolalar musiqiy o ‘yin folklorining mavzuviy tasnifi. Общество и инновации, 4(5/S), 340-345.
32. Ражабов, Т. И. (2022). Совершенствование Механизма Духовно-Нравственного Формирования Учащихся Через Народные Музыка И Песни. Miasto Przyszłości, 29, 363-367.
33. Rajabov, T. I. (2023). Distinctive Features of Folk Songs that Serve in the Spiritual and Moral Formation of Bukhara Pupils. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress, 2(3), 59-68.
34. Rajabov, T. I. (2022). The role of bukhara folklore songs in youth education in the system of continuous education.
35. Rajabov, T. I. The Mechanism of Teaching Uzbek Musical Folklore. Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences ISSN, 2795(546X), 1
36. Rajabov, T. I. (2023). Distinctive Features of Folk Songs that Serve in the Spiritual and Moral Formation of Bukhara Pupils. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress, 2(3), 59-68.
37. Madrimov, B. K., & Rajabov, T. I. (2022). Uzbek Ceremonial Folklore and its Characteristics. Nexus: Journal of Advances Studies of Engineering Science, 1(4), 53-56.
38. Rajabov, T. (2022). UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM TIZIMIDA O 'ZBEK MUSIQA FOLKLORINI O 'RGATISH DOLZARAB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 2(21), 21-31.
39. Ibovovich, T. R. (2022). PRACTICAL SITUATION OF TEACHING UZBEK MUSICAL FOLKLORE IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM. International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education, 14(6).
40. Ibovovich, R. T. (2021). EDUCATIONAL IMPORTANCE OF CHILDREN'S FOLKLORE SONGS IN MUSIC CULTURE CLASSES. Thematics Journal of Arts and Culture, 5(1).
41. Равшан, Расулов Рауфович. "ЗАМОНАВИЙ БАЙРАМЛАР РЕЖИССУРАСИДА ХАЛҚ ИЖОДИ НАМУНАЛАРИ ТАЪСИРЧАН ВОСИТА СИФАТИДА." ТА'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TANLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI (2022): 117-122.
42. Равшан, Расулов Рауфович. "ТЕАТР ТОМОШАЛАРИДА ТАЪСИРЧАН ВОСИТАЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ УСУЛЛАРИ." ТА'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TANLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI (2022): 145-151.
43. Расулов, Равшан. "ЗАМОНАВИЙ БАЙРАМЛАР РЕЖИССУРАСИДА ТАЪСИРЧАН ВОСИТАЛАРНИНГ ТУТГАН УРНИ ВА АХАМИЯТИ." TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN 1.4 (2023): 36-46.
44. Взгляды восточных мыслителей на узбекскую народную музыку. У.Х. Рамазонова Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology 3(5), 45-46
45. 45. Holmurodovna R. U. I., Oqila S. Makom art is a priority in the musical culture of Uzbekistan // Проблемы педагогики. – 2020. – №. 2 (47). – С. 87-88.
46. 46. Kholmurodovna R. U., Obidovna R. M. Social norms, sanctions and personality
47. // Вестник науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 21-2(99). – С. 115-118.
48. 47. Рамазонова У.Х., Сайфуллаева О.М. Развитие чувств у детей

49. //Проблемынауки.–2021.–№.1(60).–С.49-51.
50. 48.Ramazonova U. X., Esanova M. J. An'anaviy xonandalik rivojida maqomlarning o'rni //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3.– №. 1. – С.496-501.
51. 49.Ramazanova O. K., qizi Mustaqimova G. G. Formation and Development of National Musical Traditions //european journal of innovation in nonformal education. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 336-339.
52. 50.Рамазонова Ў. Х. ТАЛАБАЛАРДА МАЪНАВИЙ-АХЛОҚИЙ ТУШУНЧАЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ, ГУРУҲ БИЛАН ИШЛАШ ВАУНИ БОШҚАРИШ ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИ.
53. 51.Kholmurodovna U. R. Formation of publicistic performing skills in singing. – 2021.
54. 52.РамазоноваУ.Х.,ЭсановаМ.Ж.ПОДГОТОВКАМОЛОДЫХПЕВЦОВ
55. КАНСАМБЛЕВОМУВЫСТУПЛЕНИЮ//Наука,техникаиобразование.– 2021. – №. 2-1. – С. 88-91.
56. 53.Ramazanova U. H., Muhamadova M. The spiritual impact of traditional sound exercises on the minds of students. – 2022.
57. 54.RamazanovaO.K.,ShukurovM.Historicaldevelopmentofstatus.–2022.
58. 55.FeaturesofSoundRecordingintheUzbekSingingArt
59. U H Ramazonova.Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences ISSN 2795 (546X),

